

DEVELOPING THE SKILLS OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN ORGANIZING LESSONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the necessary pedagogical skills for future primary school teachers in organizing native language and literacy lessons and ways to further develop them. It also presents the experiences of foreign educators and modern methodologies.*

Keywords: *pedagogical skills, innovation, competence, qualification, modern methods, educator, primary education.*

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" extensively addresses pedagogical skills and the organization of lessons. The law requires every educator to demonstrate initiative, skill, interest, aspiration, and the ability to work with innovative ideas. Since gaining independence, new programs and textbooks have been created for primary education. Each year, new information related to innovative, modern, and information technologies is added to these textbooks, enriching them. In particular, more emphasis is being placed on analyzing literary works in the native language and reading programs, utilizing various types of assignments and technical tools for working with texts. Texts and stories that meet international standards and are included in the PIRLS system are being integrated into the textbooks. However, some teachers still retain many shortcomings related to traditional methodologies. For example, elements of rote memorization without understanding the meaning are still prevalent during lesson delivery. Many educators do not focus on analyzing pressing issues in today's economic, social, and spiritual life; rather, they require students to memorize the most important parts of the material. Such teaching methods should be avoided.

A new qualitative approach to organizing the educational process is necessary. Therefore, new ideas and constructive situations aimed at overcoming formalism in schools are being eagerly anticipated by the pedagogical community. When discussing this, it is pertinent to mention pedagogical collaboration first. Notable innovators in pedagogical collaboration include V.F. Shatalov, Y.N. Lisenkova, P.I. Volkov, M.P. Shetinin, and others. Relying on pedagogical collaboration methodologies makes the process much easier. Here, both the educator and the students are at ease, fostering mutual trust, making it easier for them, and making the educator happy as well. Below, we will explore the work of creative laboratories based on pedagogical collaboration of these innovators.

One of the key tasks facing educators is to engage students in the overall effort of education. Pedagogical collaboration is characterized by being built on the joint effort of the educator and the student in motivating them to learn. The essence of an innovative approach in dealing with students lies in the need for adequate changes in the education system due to changing social conditions. According to V.I. Juravlev, the pedagogy of collaboration requires not only relational skills but also the structure of cognitive operations, collectively acquiring knowledge, and working independently (to be the best partner).

The lesson begins with recalling and reinforcing previously acquired knowledge before transitioning to new material. This means preparing for the next topic through discussions of

previously covered subjects. The presentation of the new topic is reinforced through various exercises, and the lesson concludes with a summary, evaluation, and assignment of tasks. The engagement of students during lessons depends on how the educator organizes the class. To enhance students' learning effectiveness, it is advisable to break down the new topic into smaller segments. The extent of understanding achieved during the lesson can be assessed through various questions and assignments.

Recalling and revisiting the previous topic, along with assessing students' understanding of the new material, prepares them for its assimilation. To save time, it is beneficial for the educator to have terms, visuals, and formulas related to the new topic prepared in advance on the board. Additionally, introducing the new lesson through an oral question or problem can be effective. The posed question or problem must be interesting, surprising, and attention-grabbing for the students. The presentation of the new topic should be broken down into small segments, organized logically and sequentially, and should incorporate various teaching methods, possibly linking them to other subjects.

Managing students' activities during the lesson depends on many factors. The most crucial aspect is conveying the subject matter to the students in an engaging way. Scholars assert that interest positively influences all psychological processes and functions of a person, including perception, imagination, attention, character, and thinking. Ideas focused on nurturing children based on ancient traditions and historical-national values are essential for shaping their worldview and instilling admirable human qualities. In fact, ensuring the unity of education and upbringing and encouraging children to engage in meaningful activities can lead to effective outcomes. If the aim of education is to instill knowledge and skills that meet global standards, the purpose of upbringing is to familiarize children with life.

One of the important aspects of native language and literacy lessons is to educate children to be highly moral, spiritually mature, and responsible. Instilling feelings of friendship and a desire to perform good deeds allows children to develop holistically. Our new textbooks on native language and literacy particularly emphasize the importance of nurturing children's spiritual growth. Achieving engagement and interest in each literary work in the "Native Language and Literacy Book" and ensuring students actively listen to its content enhance their comprehension abilities. Using audio recordings of certain texts on magnetic tapes can also stimulate their engagement. The rules regarding depicting reality and objectivity in literary works, along with subjective evaluations, are of great theoretical and practical significance for methodology. Reading skills are developed during the literacy instruction process and improved in subsequent stages. Quality reading skills include reading literary texts correctly, quickly, consciously, and expressively. In native language and literacy classes, students' reading skills are shaped and refined. The qualities of reading skills are interconnected, with the foundation being conscious reading: if a student reads a text quickly and accurately but does not comprehend it, or if they read quickly to the point that others cannot understand the content, or if they read correctly but too slowly without pausing between speech units, the meaning conveyed in the text becomes unclear. Reading at a specific speed and correctly serves conscious reading; correct, quick, and conscious reading is the basis of expressive reading. Acquiring reading skills is crucial for successfully mastering all subjects taught at school. Reading is a primary form of activity that creates great opportunities for the intellectual, political, aesthetic, and verbal development of students. This process requires systematic and purposeful work on improving and refining reading skills.

Mastering reading skills is complex and requires a long time to develop. The process of developing reading skills can be divided into three stages: the analytical stage, the synthetic stage, and the automated stage. The analytical stage corresponds to the literacy instruction period, during which the skills of syllabic and phonetic analysis of words are developed. The synthetic stage is characterized by the ability to read words fluently; in this stage, recognizing words through visual perception and understanding their pronunciation aligns with understanding the meaning of the words. Students transition to the synthetic stage in the third grade. In the following years, reading becomes more automated. Examples used in shaping students' behavior and cultivating their will should inspire, excite, and delight them.

One of the essential aspects of native language and literacy lessons is to cultivate children to be morally upright, spiritually mature, and responsible. The educator's mastery and creative engagement play a vital role in instilling these qualities in the younger generation. It is crucial to awaken in them feelings of friendship and a desire to perform good deeds, enabling holistic development. Special attention is given in native language and literacy classes to ensure children grow up with refined qualities. Achieving engagement and interest in each literary work allows students to read with enthusiasm and comprehend its essence. The questions, assignments, sayings, and wise words given after each literary piece hold significant importance for children. Understanding their meanings helps them apply these lessons in their daily lives and actions.

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